

TANNING : A FUNCTION OF POLYMERS

BY S. K. BARAT

CENTRAL LEATHER RESEARCH INSTITUTE, ADYAR, MADRAS

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The two principal raw materials involved in the manufacture of leather are both composed of polymers. In the tannages with vegetable and syntan materials, collagen, composed of polycondensed amino-acids, is converted into leather by polycondensed phenolic substances. In mineral tannages also, such phenomena as olation and oxolation of basic salts are manifested as an effect of polymerisation. Tannages with semi-drying oils of marine origin also come under this class. The rates of penetration and tannage and the stability of the tan agents, so fixed into the protein network, are all greatly influenced by the polymeric structure of hides or skins and tanning agents. Even after the main tanning operation the leather has to be treated with various types of polymers in order to ensure its desirable properties. Such treatment is necessary for the strength, rigidity, wear resistance, water-proofness, uniform colour, appearance and gloss of the final leather produced. Leather is thus tanned collagen, and tanning imparts certain characteristics to the leather so produced. Some of the criteria of tannage are enumerated below so that the mechanism of tanning may be understood in its proper perspective.

Increased hydrothermal stability.—Raw collagen shrinks in water at about 60° and most tanning processes enhance this shrinkage temperature. Shrinkage temperature is a true index of the leathering effect of tanning (except in oil tanning). Since the shrinkage at 60° is due to the breaking down of lateral links between polypeptide chains¹⁻³, it follows that tannage is accompanied by an increase in the lateral cohesive forces of the protein by strengthening the existing cross-links or by forming new ones.

Resistance to enzymatic hydrolysis.—Tanning increases the capacity of the wet leather to resist the effects of proteolytic enzymes, due likely to the removal of bound water from the protein⁴ and greater rigidity between adjacent polypeptide chains as a result of tanning.

Resistance of leather to the detannisation by water.—This is measured by the chemical stability of the leather produced. This stability is effected by the tanning agents incorporated in the leather and existing in less hydrated and therefore less soluble form. Moreover, especially in case of vegetable tannins,

the tenacity of attachment with protein appears to be greatly dependent on their molecular aggregation or particle size. Higher the particle size, greater is this affinity.

Retention of fibre structure.—Raw skins generally contain about $\frac{1}{2}$ to $\frac{3}{4}$ of its weight of water which is reduced to about $\frac{1}{8}$ th in tanned leather. Most of this water exists in the capillaries between the fibres and fibrils, but a part perhaps is held by attachment to the hydrophilic groups of protein and is termed as bound water⁵. Tanning may displace this water. With the elimination of water, the capillaries, and therefore the fibre structure, tend to collapse, and the tanner attempts to retain the same by depositing tanning agents in the interstices of the fibres as in the case of vegetable tanning and in the case of chrome tanning where there is not sufficient tanning agent to do so; oil is incorporated before leather dries up.

Hides and skins are composed mainly of (i) the non-fibrous protein of the cellular structure and interfibrillary lymph and (ii) the fibrous proteins of corium which is of real interest to the tanners. The proteins under (i), viz., albumin, globulin and mucoids, are mostly removed during pretanning processes. The corium left behind after removal of these chiefly consists of three kinds of fibres, viz., collagen, reticulin and elastin. Collagen forms the bulk of corium and is composed of bundles; reticulin occurs as the encasing material for the collagen fibres which are thus held together, and elastin consists of long fine fibres which branch and reunite and exists mainly in the grain and the flesh. Collagen, however, is the main leather-forming constituent. But the properties of the finished leather depend considerably upon the state of the other two proteins.

The structure of collagen consists of a main chain of amino-acid residues linked by peptide bonds (CO.NH). Each chain terminates at one end with an amino grouping and with a COOH grouping at the other :

But unlike the synthetic polymers, the units which combine to form the long-chain molecule are not all the same but are composed of 20 different units viz., amino-acids. These units do not differ so far as their condensation into the backbone of the long-chain molecule is concerned but vary considerably as to the nature of their side-chains or R groups only. Therefore the simplest unit, like glycine possesses no projecting side-chain at all, whereas in others these side-chains may be long or short, polar or non-polar. Side-chains which contain chemically reactive groups like -OH, -COOH, -NH₂, -NH etc. are polar

in nature, that is, they are capable of forming cross bonds between adjacent molecules. In case of short R groups, backbone to backbone cross bonds are also possible. This type of cross bonding imparts compactness and stability to the adjacent molecules, which are thus rivetted together so as to form a three dimensional grid. In collagen, molecules are more or less fully extended and the fibres run in parallel. As a result, it presents a fairly well-oriented pattern.

Chibnall⁶ and Bowes⁷ have carried out comprehensive investigation as to the chemical constitution of collagen and have reported figures for the nitrogen distribution. From these it is evident that glycine residues account for about 1/3 of the molecule, whereas proline and hydroxyproline constitute about a quarter of the same. They further observe that every 10 residues consist of 3 polar and 3½ non-polar side-chains besides 3½ without any R groups. This suggests the following types of possible cross links :

(a) *Direct carbimino backbone link.*—This is possible because of the existence of 3½ units without side-chains for every 10 residues, which allow the adjacent molecular backbones to come in closer contact. This is a co-ordinate link.

Hydrogen bond can be formed between the -NH group of a protein chain and a -CO-group of the same or a neighbouring chain. Although the individual hydrogen bond is relatively weak and in most instances is broken by solution in water, a regular arrangement of long molecules with many hydrogen bonds between the molecules can be very stable.

(b) The salt link formed by the basic and acidic side chains, as for example, lysine-glutamic acid salt link.

This link is electrovalent having a length of 10½-11 Å in dry and about 15 Å in water-soaked fibre.

(c) The amide-hydroxyl link, for example, glutamine-serine.

Ratio of gram equivalents of basic group to the gram equivalent of amide group suggests that salt link will be twice as frequent as the amide link. Since out of every 10 side-chains (including the hydrogen atom contributed by glycine) three are polar; two of these therefore are capable of forming salt links.

Collagen exists either in the natural non-extensible condition or in the axially contracted condition exhibiting rubber-like property of long range elasticity. The natural wet fibre shrinks on heating to 60°.

All the above three types of links are, however, opened by the stronger organic acids in which collagen dissolves at room temperature and also by formamide and *m*-cresol on boiling.

These can be explained by the fact that in the natural state collagen fibre exists with the long polymeric molecules, fully stretched and stabilised by at least two chemically different types of cross links. But in the axially contracted state, one type of the cross link has been ruptured by experimental condition, while the other still holds on. The opening of one type of cross link leads to the crumpling of a section of the fibre, thereby causing an overall shortage in length and consequent gain in entropy. The existence of the other type of cross link, however, still maintains the fibre structure. In the extreme case of breakdown of all links, the long molecules split into individual units and the fibre dissolves.

In collagen fibre there are no strong lateral bonds of co-valent type, and hence, in converting collagen fibre into leather fibre, the weaker cross bonds of natural fibre have to be replaced by stronger ones built up by tanning agents. Much of the physical properties in the final leather depend on the state in which collagen fibres have been tanned, *i.e.*, the degree of plumpness, extension, contraction, etc.

Among the natural vegetable tannins are polyhydroxy phenolic condensation products. These form one of the essential constituents of barks, wood, fruits etc., and are feebly acidic and astringent in taste. Some tannins hydrolyse to produce polyhydroxybenzene carboxylic acid (such as gallic acid) and neutral polyhydroxy compounds like sugars, whereas others resist this breakdown into the smaller units but are converted into more complex, amorphous and insoluble compounds. On the basis of these characteristics, these are broadly classified into (i) *hydrolysable tannins* and (ii) *condensed tannins*.

Tannins under (i) comprise mutual esters of phenolic carboxylic acids giving rise to depsides, and esters of phenolic carboxylic acids or depsides in which the alcoholic components are sugars, and glucosides of depsides. Tannins under (ii) are more complex in nature and include polyhydroxybenzophenone

and compounds derivable from polyhydroxyflavans. These include tannins which produce phlobaphenes or tanner's reds which by virtue of their steric properties tend to form difficultly soluble molecular aggregates.

In actual tanning process, condensation of tan molecules with one another may occur leading to a further condensation or association of these tan molecules and collagen⁹. The OH- group of vegetable tan may react with NH₂ group of hide forming

which passes into more stable form R₂-NH-R₁. With some tannins the salt formation between tan acids and amino groups of collagen side-chain (Zwitterions) may be more important⁹, but it cannot be the only mode of combination as the acid groups in catechol tans are not strong enough to form salts at the pH value of the vegetable tanning.

All naturally occurring vegetable tans are large molecules capable of multipoint hydrogen bonding. According to Shuttleworth¹⁰ these are surrounded in the process of tanning by solvent (water) molecules, hydrogen bonded at numerous points over the surface of the molecule, thereby rendering them compatible with the solvent as a whole. The protein molecules, though insoluble for structural reasons, are also capable of multipoint hydrogen bonding,

the chief sites being the $\begin{array}{c} -\text{NH}-\text{C} \\ \vdots \quad \parallel \\ \text{O} \dots \end{array}$ groups, the hydroxyproline groups and

the side-chain amino and carboxyl groups. In aqueous medium the protein molecules are separated by both hydrogen bonded and free water to an extent depending on swelling. The tannin molecules diffuse along the protein molecules and become hydrogen bonded to the protein, the firmness of fixation depending on the number of points and bond strength of attachment. This may involve the displacement of water from the reactive groups in protein⁴ and formation of cross links in the protein structure, thereby increasing its hydrothermal stability.

Besides these natural vegetable tan materials, the tanner now has a series of synthetic tanning agents at his disposal, viz., the syntans. These are generally made by linking together aromatic nuclei of coal-tar distillation products like phenol, cresol, naphthalene and derivatives, by means of various bridging agents like formaldehyde ($-\text{CH}_2-$ bridge), acetaldehyde

$\begin{array}{c} \text{Me} \\ | \\ (-\text{CH}-\text{bridge}), \text{ acetone } \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{Me} \\ | \\ -\text{C}-\text{bridge} \\ | \\ \text{Me} \end{array} \right) \text{ and introducing the minimum number} \end{array}$

of sulphonic (salt) groups so as to obtain the desirable solubility or dispersi-

bility in water. Catechol, resorcin and Colophony (natural resins) have also been used. Croad¹¹ was able to prepare an improved type of syntan of higher molecular weight and containing less sulphonic groupings. First a synthetic resin of Novolak type was made from phenol and formaldehyde. The large molecule so produced was made soluble with much less H_2SO_4 as :

Some of the above reactions are involved in manufacturing typical products like 'Extra B' which are sketched as :

According to Küntzel¹² the mechanism of reaction between collagen and syntan involves some sort of hydrogen bonding between groups (e.g. peptide links) in the collagen molecule and hydrogen atoms in the aromatic nuclei of the tannins. Substituents in the aromatic nuclei encourage this mechanism by exerting a sort of 'activating effect' on these hydrogen atoms. This postulate suggests that the sulphone link activates *meta* position to a greater extent than does the methylene link. Hence, replacement of methylene link by sulphone links induces a greater affinity for collagen. Hydroxyl and thiol groups activate *ortho* and *para* positions. Therefore simultaneous presence of hydroxyl and sulphone links ensures extra affinity for collagen.

In tanning it is desirable to have a fairly large molecular size and poly-disperse systems. Therefore mixed cresols are used in practice, because the different rates of condensation of *o*-, *m*- and *p*- isomers result in aggregated molecules of various sizes,

Metallic salts, which are generally used in the tanning industry, viz., Cr, Al, Fe, Zr etc., have a co-ordination number of 6, *i.e.*, they are capable of forming complex ions in which 6 neutral molecules or anions are associated with the metallic ion. The ability to form such complexes varies with different metals and different anions.

Hence, on the basis of Werner-Pfeiffer hypothesis the hydrolysis of such salts may be represented as :

where X is a monovalent anion and me, a metal. Bjerrum¹³ found that when acid was added to a solution, which had previously been made basic, only a part of the acid was acted upon immediately and the rest was neutralised slowly. He ascribed this resistance to acid to the hydroxy groups being firmly held owing to the agglomeration of two or more complexes. Stiasny¹⁴ elucidated the same conception with particular reference to chromium salts as follows.

This is termed as 'olation' and it may lead to larger aggregates as :

The mechanism of tannage with basic mineral salts of Cr, Al, Zr, Fe etc. most probably involves co-ordination of suitable groups in protein (e.g. CO₂-, NH₂-, -OH, -CONH- etc.) into the metal complex. This combination also displaces water from both the participants and forms cross bonds between protein molecules, resulting in an appreciable increase in shrinkage temperature.

The collagen-chrome complex reaction is two-fold, both acidic and basic groups in the protein molecule being involved. Mechanism of chrome tanning perhaps consists in the formation of co-ordination complexes between the

protein and the metallic ion or complex. Küntzel and Riess¹⁵ suggest that the carboxyl group of collagen enters the chrome complex in the same manner as anions of organic acids, followed by the formation of links with the basic group of adjacent polypeptide chain. According to Gustavson¹⁶ chrome tanning is a multipoint attachment of positively charged Cr complex to the negatively charged carboxyl group of collagen leading to the direct association of carboxyl group with Cr atom of the complex by conversion of the labile electrovalent link, initiating the reaction to the stable co-ordinate co-valent link of the final Cr-collagen compound. The hydrolysed and some of the complex-bound acid may combine with the basic group of collagen.

Tannages with semi-drying oil of marine origin like Cod, Herring etc. involve oxidation of the oil leading to the formation of acrolein which is responsible for effecting tannage. It has been established¹⁷ that acrolein reacts with amino group of collagen producing a leather with a shrinkage temperature of 82°. The cross-bond formation in this case may be represented as :

where R is the polypeptide molecules of protein.

Formaldehyde tannage also involves amino groups of the protein and forms cross links of the type R—NH—CH₂—NH—R. Combination with guanidine group also occurs.

In short, tanning therefore initiates formation of new cross bonds or reinforcement of the existing ones in the collagen network by means of complex tanning agents. In course of tannage most of the lyophilic groups in the hide collagen are transformed into lyophobic ones. This transformation is effected by reactions between the active groups of the collagen and hydroxy groups of the tanning agents due to secondary valencies on both components, as in case of vegetable, mineral and fat tannages or by reactions between hide and tanning agents involving primary valencies as in case of formaldehyde tannage.

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